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Historical Sciences

SOCIAL POLICY OF STATE IN MODERN RUSSIA

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Abstract:

This article primarily addresses the issue of state social policy. Social policy plays a huge role in the domestic policy of any state, since problems arising in the social sphere are directly related to the development of the economic and political life of the country, and therefore are a kind of indicator of the development of society.

The study of social policy issues has long been in the spotlight. Social policy, being one of the most important components of state activity, should not only mitigate negative social phenomena, but also help the population adapt to new conditions, promote social support for reforms, implement positive changes in the economy, ensure social orientation of the population.

For modern Russia, this issue today is particularly relevant due to the need to form a new model of social policy. At present, first of all, it is necessary to find a solution regarding the role of the state in the new social policy, its functions and interaction with public institutions.

Keywords: social politics, social protection, social sector, prosperity, development, population, government.

I. INTRODUCTION

Social policy, being the most important sphere of interests of modern society and an important part of the modern state activity obviously needs a single definition. Nowadays a lot of opinions about the meaning of the concept and structure of social politics have been accumulated. This due to the fact that social policy is closely connected with the type and level of development of society, the prevailing mentality of the population, with the targets and tasks that society puts in front of him in its social development.

The prosperity of citizens directly depends on the social politics of the state. However, it is the human factor that influences it to the highest degree. This is due to the fact that social politics is associated with the mentality of the population, the targets that society sets itself. The concept of “social policy” is used to refer to the politics used by the government to ensure prosperity and social protection, ways to develop social prosperity and academic study of the subject. From the position of scientists, the term “social politics” is a politics of regulating the social sphere. The theoretical foundations of social policy were first developed in the second half of the 19th century. German scientists have made the greatest contribution to the development of this theoretical basis. They created a “coterie of social politics study” (“Verein hir Sozialpolitik”), which attracted the interest of researchers to the difficulties of settlement social processes from other capitalist countries.

Developed several models of social policy:

The first is the “Residual model of social policy” (residual). This model appeared in England in 1531 with the creation of laws on the poor in order to regulate the impoverishment of residents. According to the principle of the residual model, the state provides its population with only the most necessary services (it provides assistance to the needy from funds that have not been used by public funds). The main idea of this model is to train the population to dispense with state support.

The second is the “State-redistributive model of social politics” (meritocratic). It was appeared thanks to the activities of trade union organizations, ideas of social equality. It implies a social insurance system as the main component of the system of social protection of citizens. Social assistance is provided on the basis of individual situations. The source of funding in the state-redistributive model is social funds.

The third one is “The Model of Industrial and Economic Development”. In this model, social protection covers assistance, insurance, and health care. The basis is that social needs are satisfied only with the active work and discipline of the working part of society. The sources of funding for this are the insurance premiums of workers and entrepreneurs, while the state bears a third of all the costs of servicing pensioners.

II. METHODOLOGY

The methodology of social policy as a science is a culture of scientific thought. In the science of social policy there is a theoretical and methodological diversity. The essence of the methodology is how the research is conducted, how its results are put into practice. These special questions are posed and solved in the course of theoretical statements and developments and together with them. With a superficial perception of social policy, its scientific research is limited to certain informative characteristics, and often only to specific phenomenal forms.

In the study of social policy, social development, general scientific methods and specific methods are used, which are determined by the research of a specific science and academic discipline.

In this work, several methods were used to study the problems of the issue.

The historical method allowed us to analyze the stages of development of a phenomenon.

The method of comparative analysis revealed the similarities and differences between the phenomena in question in one area, industry, in order to establish common and specific characteristics for them, trends and indicators.

The method of structural analysis helped to study the individual structural components of the system. The use of the structural analysis method made it possible to analyze social sectors as separate structures of the social complex of the state. The theoretical and methodological basis for the study was the statistics and the works of Russian and foreign economists and scientists, such as Dobrenkov VI, Lavrienko IM, Sumtsova N.V. and etc.

III. DISCUSSION

The problems of social policy will be relevant for a long time nowadays, since the social state exists when there is a civil society in it that relies on the ideas of the rule of law. The social state is the main model of politics in European countries, a social guarantor, and a sign of high life goals and standards of society. The concept of a “social state” was first put forward in 1842 by German state historian and economist Lorenz von Stein. He believed that the main functions of the state - to promote the economic and social progress of all citizens, maintaining equality in rights for all classes of the population.

Subsequently, the theory of the social state that emerged in the 19th century was embodied in European countries as a result of the struggle of the working class defending its rights. Friedrich Naumann continued to develop the idea of a social state. He and his supporters set before the state the task of materially and morally improving the position of the lower classes by resorting to broad social reforms, and not only protect property and social order. This led to the formation of a liberal model of social politics. This model is subdivided into social democratic, corporate, self-liberal, “social economy”, market and rudimentary. Consider some of them.

The social democratic model of the (Scandinavian) social policy is characteristic of Denmark, Sweden, and Finland. This model carries in itself the idea of unity of all strata of the population and all socio-economic groups. Social security comes at the expense of taxes (about a third of the state budget is spent). Social services are perceived as rights of citizens. The working population has additional benefits. Unemployment insurance is sold on a voluntary basis. The characteristic features of the social democratic model are: the quality and availability of social services, a high level of social security. The corporate model of social policy is in many respects close to the social democratic model. It was formed during the period of historical upheavals, when the state assumed all control functions. It received in France, Germany, Austria, and Italy. The essence of this model is that the state is the only public institution that does not have its own interests and is able to act between classes of society, depending on their interests. In the corporate model, the state supports the unemployed, creates employment programs, re-prepares and conducts vocational guidance for those who have lost their jobs, thereby significantly improving the quality of the workforce, and provides social guarantees.

The model of “social market economy” of social politics was implemented in Germany. The growing importance of market beginnings in the social sphere instead of extensive state intervention is the main idea of this model. The market nature of the provision of all social services predominates, which gives independence to the consumer of these services, creates competition with individual organizations and institutions in the social sphere. At the same time, the implementation of all social programs of the state required a large and inefficient bureaucracy, which has a low degree of responsibility for its activities.

The rudimentary social policy model has gained ground in southern Europe over the past couple of decades. The degree of social security in the countries of Southern Europe is rather low than the social protection of the population is mostly carried out by family and private charity. This model of social policy is usually called developing (transitional). Under the influence of socio-economic and structural changes, general social security systems are created or improved, containing in their structure social insurance and insurance in production.

Nowadays there are quite a large number of works focused on research in the social environment, mainly in the fields of economics, political science, and jurisprudence, which reflect various aspects of social policy. Our compatriots gained experience in conducting sociological research. These works were presented in the works of V.G. Grechikhin, V.I. Shalenko, A.N. Kolesnikov, P.S. Romanov and others. The results of these studies are already being applied in the development of strategies for managing the social sphere. However, such scientific developments, where the sociological aspects of social policy management and the protection of the population would be considered, are still insufficient.

IV. RESULTS

The relevance of the topic of social policy is confirmed by the Constitution of the Russian Federation. Article 7 of the Constitution of the Russian Federation says as follows:

1. The Russian Federation is a social State whose policy is aimed at creating conditions for a worthy life and the unhindered development of man.

2. In the Russian Federation the labor and health of people shall be protected, guaranteed minimum wages and salaries shall be established, state support ensured for the family, maternity, paternity and childhood, for disabled persons and the elderly, a system of social services developed, state pensions, allowances and other social security guarantees shall be established.

Recently, in Russian society there have been favorable changes that formed a certain basis for increasing its ability to modernize, positive changes and progression. Today there are a number of elements for the transition to a strong social policy, which consists in creating the necessary conditions for a more rational management.

At the same time, the formation of a socially oriented economy is complicated in our country. One of the reasons was repeatedly singled out by the Chairman of the Government of the Russian Federation, Dmitry Anatolyevich Medvedev, a bureaucratic management practice, sometimes acting to the detriment of social targets. The second reason can be identified significant technical lag leading industries, and therefore not met a number of the needs of the population. In addition, the presence of consumer mood in society, which must it, be taken into account during the formation of the social policy of the state.

According to the provisions of the National Security Concept of the Russian Federation, adopted in 2000, "the priority of economic factors in the social sphere is crucial for strengthening the state, for real state provision of social guarantees, for developing mechanisms of collective responsibility and democratic decision-making, social partnership. At the same time, it is important to conduct socially fair and cost-effective income distribution policies. " In the National Security Strategy of the Russian Federation, which entered into force on May 12, 2009, socio-economic goals were followed.

According to scientists, the guarantee of political stability and civil consent is the main problem of modern social politics. This is realistic to achieve a balance between the financial profit of citizens and commodity reserves, the demand of citizens for the quantity of goods and services, the creation of a solid foundation for the development of education, culture, spirituality, and the improvement of public health.

In Russian sociology, the term "social politics" as a scientific concept appeared relatively recently. However, throughout the history of mankind, social policy variations have been developed by different types of societies and implemented by different states. The basis for this was people's ideas about morality, religious beliefs, and traditions. Thus, social policy existed before, but it was a consequence of the general development of mankind, rather than the specific activities of people and states.

So, in the middle of the 19th century, there was a social legislation. A little later, the first enshrined social rights appeared: the right to work and its favorable conditions, the right to rest, the right to an adequate standard of living, the right to education. In the 20th century, the concept of the social state was implemented; state principles were based on the principles of social law.

On the "shoulders" of the social state falls:

1) The high level of wages for the able-bodied strata of the population. Only the labor of citizens contains the state and its population as a whole, since they are the main source of taxation.

2) A sufficient level of satisfaction by citizens of their needs.

3) Advanced education, health care and other social services.

4) Social justice.

5) Solving social conflicts.

6) Reliable social protection for disabled citizens.

A person in a social state has the right to demand the provision of social needs at a decent level. The state, in turn, meets social needs at a level that is possible by economic development, traditions, cultural and political values. Summarizing, the function of the state to meet the social needs of the population is defined as its social policy. The priority areas of social protection and provision of the necessary standard of living are: Indexation of incomes of the population: a set of measures to increase the real consumer content of the basic incomes of the population ("On indexation of incomes and savings of the population" in 1991). Also it provides minimum social guarantees for income, the most important - the cost of living. ("On the subsistence minimum in the Russian Federation"). Regulation of minimum standards and regulations: minimum regulatory expenditures of the consolidated budget for education, health care, housing, social services, etc.

The head of the problem is financial insecurity, therefore, at present, the benefits are being converted into targeted social benefits, saving them only for the poor (housing subsidy). Compulsory social insurance is intended to compensate for material losses caused by temporary or permanent termination of work due to age, illness, work injury (payment of pensions, sick pay, unemployment benefits, etc.). Social security - aimed at maintaining disabled members of society: the elderly, the disabled, children, people who have lost their breadwinner. This system also includes social services: nursing homes stay centers, prosthetics.

Social assistance: it is not permanent and is of a purely specific, individual character. The criterion of the right to this type of assistance is determined by the income below the subsistence minimum per family member. Today, the term "social policy" refers to the number of concepts used in official documents of state-building. However, in extensive scientific discussions, the content of this concept varies greatly among different scientists. Consequently, there is still no single scientific definition formulating the concept of "social policy". Over the history of human development, many different definitions, concepts and approaches to "social policy" have accumulated. This diversity has led to a diversity of points of view to the formation and implementation of social policies.

Social politics is divided into different subtypes of policy. The degree of development of social policy is determined by the development of economic, tax, domestic, foreign and other specific policies. From this it follows that social policy itself cannot exist separately from state policy. The main purpose of the social politics of the state is to improve the health of the population, to provide decent income and social support in specific adverse life situations and, in general, to create a favorable social atmosphere for society. Therefore, the importance of social policy determines its impact on technical, cultural and spiritual development, labor productivity, and the qualification of the workforce.

Initially, basic human needs were met by others public institutions: families, communities. And with the development of religion were started needing charitable institutions. But these institutions do not have the necessary mechanisms, levers and means that are necessary to meet the social needs of all segments of the population at a level that impedes social tension and contributes to stability in society.

By its activity, the state and public organizations form a social policy in the form of an impact on a society of managerial nature in order to ensure the development of an individual, society as a whole, social stability, reproductive function, and livelihoods. In a general sense, the direction of social policy is to establish a balance of social needs with the living conditions of the population, eliminating the state of need, which is generated by the inability to realize the needs of the individual independently. However, one should not allow total state intervention in the social sphere, since the numerous regulations of all social relations will lead to a regression of the social sphere. Therefore, when establishing a state social policy, it is necessary to take into account all its possibilities, and paying attention to specific areas, do not forget about others.

After analyzing the above, we can say that social policy as a scientific definition is a concept consisting of complexes, which characterizes the ideological ideas of the state and society about the directions of social development, on the one hand, and their specific activities for achieving social successes corresponding to these goals. In the concept of social protection of citizens, social policy has its own specifics, determined by the forms of implementation, targets and tasks. Ultimately, when social policy includes the interests of social groups and classes, creates stability in society, inspires optimism and gives people confidence, it can be humanistic, socially just and modern.

V. CONCLUSION

In conclusion of this work it can be concluded that the existing problems in the social policy of the state require an immediate solution. It is on the social welfare depends on the efficiency of production, the welfare of the state. First of all, a normal standard of living should be created for ordinary citizens (middle class). Social care of the state for its citizens requires large financial investments. At first glance, an invisible return on these investments will increase the well-being of not only the population, but also the state itself. The way in which the state conducts social programs can be judged on the standard of living of the poorest segments of society and how much this group occupies in the total population of the country. Therefore, the effective social policy of the state is one of the priorities of the transition to market relations and the exit of the Russian economy from the crisis.

Every year, the president and the heads of both chambers of the Federal Assembly of Russia address with the joint social message to the people of Russia, containing the main provisions of the social policy for the current year. These messages specify the provisions of the "Social Doctrine" and the "Social Strategy of the Russian Federation", the implementation of which will streamline the relationship between social and economic decisions and actions of government at all levels of government, create an effective and flexible systems of social development priorities economic progress.

For the most fruitful activities in the formation, implementation and monitoring of the implementation of social policy, all branches and state authorities in the Russian Federation, local governments, public organizations and society as a whole, employers and the business community should participate as subjects. In turn, all categories and segments of the population, public and territorial organizations and groups, and also branches of the social sphere should become objects of social policy.

REFERENCES

Ashmarov, I.A. (2006). Monetary policy and labour market. The development of financial relations in modern Russia: *intercollege collection of scientific articles. Voronezh: Istoki Publishers*. Pp. 15-19. (in Russ.).

Ashmarov, I.A. (2009). On the issue of socio-economic transformations in modern Russia. Risk and danger society of the 21st century: *forecasts, scenarios for overcoming the crisis: the works of Vseross. scientific conference. Voronezh: Voronezh State Technical University*. Pp. 124-127. (in Russ.).

Ashmarov, I.A. (2009). Social and institutional features of the modern Russian economy. *Vestnik Voronezhskogo gosudarstvennogo tekhnicheskogo universiteta. Bulletin of the Voronezh State Technical University. V. 5. №. 3. Pp. 22-24.* (in Russ.).

Ashmarov, I.A. (2017). The value of state financial policy for the development of the economy and social sphere. Socio-political processes in the modern world: the view of the young: *materials of the student's scientific-practical conference. January 17, 2017 Voronezh: Editorial and Publishing Department of the Voronezh Branch of the RANEPa*. Pp. 13-19. (in Russ.)

Constitution of the Russian Federation (2014) passed by nation-wide voting of December 12, 1993, Article 7.

Dobrenkov V.I., Kravchenko A.I. (2002) *Sociology: a short course*. Pp. 231-235.

Ershov, B.A., (2012) Historiographical aspects of the relationship between the Russian Orthodox Church and state structures in the provinces of the Central Chernozem region in the XIX -early XX centuries. *Bulletin of the Voronezh State Technical University. Series "Humanities"*. Pp. 188-192.

Ershov, B.A., (2012) State legal regulation of the activities of the Russian Orthodox Church in the provinces of the Central Chernozem region in the XIX -early XX centuries *Historical, philosophical, political and legal sciences, culturology and arthistory. Questions of theory and practice*. Pp. 75-78.

Ershov, B.A., (2012) The Russian Orthodox Church in the system of public relations in the XIX– early XX centuries. (on materials of Central-Black earth Provinces) *dissertation for the degree of Doctor of Historical Sciences / Kursk State University*. 412 p.

Ershov, B.A., (2013) Russian Orthodox Church in the structure of public administration in the XIX - early XX centuries: *Monograph Voronezh State Technical University*. 245 p.

Esping-Andersen G. (1990) *The Three World of Welfare Capitalism*. Pp. 26-33.

Evstrakov A.E. (2005) The Genesis of the Idea of the Welfare State: Historical and Theoretical Problems.

Kholostova E.I., Sovrina A.S. (2004) *Social work: theory and practice*.

Lavrienko I.M. (2000) *State Social Policy of the Russian Federation: Experience and Transformation Problems (80s - first half of the 20th century of the 20th century)*. Pp. 54-59.

Maslova L.A. (2004) Improvement of organizational forms of management of the system of social protection of the population in the region. Pp.16-17.

Panarin A.S. (2002) *Temptation of globalism*. Pp. 415-416.

Perevozchikova L.S., Ershov B.A., Ashmarov I.A., Volkova E.A. (2017) Role of Russian Orthodox Church in life of peasants in Russia in XIX - the beginning of the XX-th centuries *Bylye Gody Russian Historical Journal. №. 43 (1)*. Pp. 121-128.

Platonov N.A., Shumaeva V.A., Butieva I.V. (2008) *State regulation of the national economy*.

Romanovskaya E.S., (2007) *Transformation of the system of social protection of the population: the experience of sociological research*. Pp. 6-90.

Sumtsova N.V. (2003) *Economic Theory*.

Titmuss R., (1974) *Social Policy An Introduction*. Pp. 30-31.